

**OILAVIY TADBIRKORLIK VA BIZNESNI QO'LLAB-
QUVVATLASH MASALALARI**

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Farg'ona viloyati Oltiariq tumani

2 son kasb hunar maktabi tadbirkorlik va

biznes asoslari fani o'qituvchisi

Annotasiya: Maqolada O'zbekistonda oilalarni iqtisodiy qo'llab quvvatlash maqsadida oilaviy tadbirkorlikka keng yo'l osilishi va buni huquqiy asoslari qisqacha tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Iqtisod, biznes, tadbirkorlik, oila, qonun

Аннотация: В статье кратко анализируются широкий подход к семейному предпринимательству в Узбекистане с целью экономической поддержки семей и его правовая основа.

Ключевые слова: экономика, бизнес, предпринимательство, семья, право

Abstract: The article briefly analyzes the broad approach to family entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan for the purpose of economic support for families and its legal basis.

Key words: economics, business, entrepreneurship, family, law

Mamlakatimizda tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish va uning huquqiy himoyasini ta'minlash – amalga oshirilayotgan iqtisodiy islohotlarning eng asosiy yo'nalishi hisoblanadi. Zero, tadbirkorlik rivoji – yurtimiz va iqtisodiyotimiz taraqqiyoti garovidir.

SHu bois ham istiqlolning dastlabki kunlaridan boshlab Prezidentimizning bevosita rahbarligida yurtimizda iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy va huquqiy sohalarni isloh

etish, erkin tadbirkorlik faoliyatini qaror toptirish borasidagi islohotlar mantiqiy izchillikda bosqichma-bosqich amalga oshirib kelinmoqda.

Xususan, so'nggi yillarda qabul qilingan O'zbekiston Respublikasi qonunlari, Prezident farmonlari, qarorlari hamda Hukumat qarorlari natijasida tadbirkorlik subyektlarini ro'yxatga olishning xabardor qilish tartibi joriy etildi, ularning moliya-xo'jalik faoliyatini faqat soliq idoralari tekshirishi mumkinligi va tadbirkorlarga nisbatan har qanday sanksiyalar sud qaroriga binoan qo'llanilishi belgilandi, shuningdek hisobot taqdim etishning barcha shakllari va turlari, tadbirkorlar faoliyatiga asossiz aralashuv va tekshirishlar soni keskin qisqartirildi.

2012 yil 26 aprelda "Oilaviy tadbirkorlik to'g'risida"gi Qonun qabul qilindi. Mazkur Qonun 35 moddadan iborat bo'lib, uning asosiy maqsadi oilaviy tadbirkorlik sohasidagi munosabatlarni tartibga solishdan iborat.

Ushbu qonun bilan tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishda quyidagi imtiyozlar berilgan:

- Oilaviy korxonalar tadbirkorlik subyekti sifatida yuridik shaxsning tashkiliy-huquqiy shakli hamda kichik tadbirkorlik subyekti sifatida belgilandi;
- Oilaviy korxonalar ishtirokchilari oila a'zolarining shaxsiy mehnatiga asoslangan bir paytda qonun hujjatlariga muvofiq xodimlarni yollashni amalga oshirishi mumkin;
- Oilaviy korxonalar boshlig'i o'zgargan, ishtirokchi oilaviy korxonalar tarkibiga ixtiyoriy ravishda kirgan (undan chiqib ketgan), er va xotin o'rtasidagi nikoh bekor qilingan yoki oilaviy korxonalar ishtirokchisi vafot etgan va bu hollar oilaviy korxonalar balansiga berilgan oilaviy korxonalar ishtirokchilarining mol-mulki ro'yxatida o'zgarishlarga sabab bo'lgan taqdirda, ta'sis shartnomasiga tegishli o'zgartish va qo'shimchalar kiritiladi. Bunda oilaviy korxonani qayta davlat ro'yxatidan o'tkazish talab qilinmaydi;
- Oilaviy korxonalar qonun hujjatlarida belgilanadigan tartibda yagona soliq to'lovini to'lovchiligi va Oilaviy korxonaning foydasi soliqlar va boshqa majburiy

to'lovlar to'langanidan keyin uning ishtirokchilari tasarrufiga o'tadi hamda unga soliq solinmaydi;

- Oilaviy korxonalar ishtirokchilariga mulk huquqi asosida tegishli bo'lgan turar joylarni ulardan oilaviy korxonalar faoliyatida foydalanish maqsadida yashash uchun mo'ljallanmagan joylarga aylantirish talab qilinmaydi, bundan faoliyatning ayrim turlari uchun qonun hujjatlarida nazarda tutilgan hollar mustasno.

Bundan tashqari, qonunda oilaviy korxonalar faoliyatini tekshirishlarning cheklanishi belgilangan bo'lib, unga ko'ra oilaviy korxonaning moliya-xo'jalik faoliyatini rejali tekshirishlar ko'pi bilan to'rt yilda bir marta amalga oshirilishi belgilangan.

Yangi tashkil etilgan oilaviy korxonaning moliya-xo'jalik faoliyati u davlat ro'yxatidan o'tkazilgan paytdan e'tiboran dastlabki uch yil mobaynida rejali tekshiruvlardan o'tkazilmaydi, bundan byudjet mablag'laridan va markazlashtirilgan mablag'lardan hamda resurslardan maqsadli foydalanish bilan bog'liq tekshirishlar mustasno.

Eng ahamiyatli joyi shundan iboratki, Qonunning 28-moddasida oilaviy korxonalar turar joydan bir vaqtning o'zida unda istiqomat qilgan holda tovarlar ishlab chiqarish (ishlar bajarish, xizmatlar ko'rsatish) uchun foydalangan taqdirda, kommunal infratuzilma xizmatlari (elektr energiyasi, suv ta'minoti, kanalizatsiya, gaz ta'minoti va issiqlik ta'minoti) haqini to'lash aholi uchun belgilangan tariflar bo'yicha va shartlar asosida amalga oshirilishi, kommunal xizmat ko'rsatish, elektr va gaz ta'minoti korxonalar zarur kommunikatsiya tarmoqlarining oilaviy korxonalar faoliyati amalga oshirilayotgan joygacha yetkazilishini hamda ulanishini aholi uchun belgilangan tariflar bo'yicha va shartlar asosida ta'minlashi belgilab qo'yildi.

Mazkur qabul qilingan narmativ-huquqiy hujjatlar bilan tadbirkorlikning huquqlarini himoya qilish, ular faoliyatini takomillashtirishning huquqiy mexanizmi yaratilishi masalaning bir tomoni bo'lsa, uni amaliyotga to'g'ri samarali

joriy etish muhim hisoblanadi. Bu esa bizdan chuqur bilim va malaka eng avvalo fidoiylilikni talab qiladi.

Bu esa barcha davlat idoralari qatori adliya organlariga ham katta mas'uliyat yuklaydi. SHu munosabat bilan Buxoro viloyat adliya boshqarmasi tadbirkorlik subyektlari faoliyatiga to'sqinlik qilish va ularning huquqlarini buzilishi holatlarga chek qo'yish, tadbirkorlikka oid qonun hujjatlariga rioya qilinishini yaxshilash, sohaga oid normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar mazmun-mohiyatini tadbirkorlik subyektlariga yetkazish maqsadida joylarda doimiy tarzda o'rganish ishlari, shuningdek targ'ibot tadbirlarini ham olib bormoqda.

Xususan, tadbirkorlikka oid qonun hujjatlarning mazmun-mohiyatini keng targ'ib qilish maqsadida tegishli idoralar bilan hamkorlikda 2012 yilning o'tgan davri davomida joylarda jami yuzga yaqin targ'ibot ishlari olib borildi.

SHu bilan birga, adliya boshqarmasiga tadbirkorlik subyektlari tomonidan berilgan ariza va shikoyatlarni hamda "Ishonch telefoni" orqali qilingan jami 19 ta murojaatlar kelib tushgan bo'lib, ularning 38,8 foizi qanoatlantirilgan.

Adliya boshqarmasi tomonidan nazorat qiluvchi va davlat boshqaruvi organlarini tadbirkorlar faoliyatiga noqonuniy aralashuvlarini oldini olish maqsadida ular faoliyati muntazam ravishda o'rganib borilmoqda. Xususan, o'tkazilgan o'rganishlar davomida ular faoliyatida mingga yaqin turli qonunbuzarlik holatlariga yo'l qo'yilganligi aniqlangan.

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